

EARTH SCIENCES

POSSIBILITIES OF UNDERGROUND GRAVITY EXPLORATION

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the question of the possibility of using underground gravity prospecting for exploration of mineral deposits, in particular ore minerals and hydrocarbon deposits. As is known, recently in the world practice of applying geophysical methods, digital instruments are widely used, which provide high accuracy of measured geophysical data. In particular, gravimagnetic work is being carried out in Azerbaijan using digital gravimeters and magnetometers, which ensures the high efficiency of geophysical work. Underground gravity exploration covers gravimetric work in wells and mines and other underground structures and workings. Underground gravimetric work is usually carried out in conditions of approaching to anomalous geological objects, which provides amplification the intensity of the recorded gravimetric data on the one hand and makes it possible to clarify the location of the desired minerals and, in particular, ore bodies. The article analyzes the question of the possibility and effectiveness of underground gravimetric work on the basis of individual practical examples in the world practice.

Keywords: underground gravity, borehole gravimetry, gravity anomaly, mine gravimetry, Fay's correction, analytical continuation of the gravity field, ore body.

Introduction

In the search and exploration of prospecting and exploration of mineral deposits and ore deposits, underground, or mine, gravity prospecting is increasingly being used. In some cases, it is also used in solving some other problems: searching for deposits of coal, salt, etc. Gravimetric observations in mines are carried out to search for missed and deep-lying ore bodies, the anomalous effect of which on the day surface is insignificant. A number of works in world practice have been devoted to the issue of gravimetric work in underground conditions (Mironov, 1977; Chico and Raymundo, 1964; Domzalski, Fajklewics and Glinski, 1982; Vasiljević and etc., 1914; Schultz, 1989; Nind and etc.; Butler and Dwain, 1984; Alixant and Mann, 1995). In all these works, the results of gravimetric work carried out in underground workings as well as in borehole conditions are presented. These results, as well as the performed studies on the modeling of gravity data, show the importance of field and underground (including directly downhole) gravity operations.

The purpose of our research is to study gravimetric materials obtained in the field on certain areas in world practice (since such work has not yet been carried out in our country) and, based on the interpretation and processing of these materials in a modern interface, to show the possibility and efficiency of carrying out gravimetric work in underground conditions.

Means and methods

It should be noted that field work carried out in underground conditions, including in wells, has its own specifics. As is known, when gravimetric operations are performed on the earth's surface at relief points, corrections for height, intermediate layer, and relief are introduced into the observed values of gravity when calculating the anomaly. The gravity anomaly, taking into account the Faye correction (correction for height), has the following form:

$$\Delta g = g_{\text{obs}} \pm 0,3086 h \cdot \gamma_0 \quad (1)$$

where g_{obs} are the observed values of gravity (acceleration of gravity); h is the height of the observation point above sea level; γ_0 is the normal value of gravity, calculated by the Helmert or Cassinis formula (Fig.1). And the gravity anomaly, taking into account the correction for the height

and the intermediate layer (Bouguer anomaly), is calculated by the following formula:

$$\Delta g_{\text{Buge}} = g_{\text{obs}} \pm (0,3086 - 0,0419\sigma) h \quad (2)$$

where σ is the density of the intermediate layer (Fig. 2).

Fig.1. On the definition of Faye's gravity anomaly

Fig.2. On the definition of the Bouguer gravity anomaly

In the case of borehole gravity surveys, measurements are made along the borehole using a borehole gravimeter with a certain step of moving the device from top to bottom. It can be shown that in this case only the correction for the intermediate layer is used. Moreover, as an intermediate layer, separate geological layers are used, which differ in density. The densities of these layers are determined by the formula:

$$g_2 - g_1 = 4\sigma\pi\Delta h \quad (3)$$

Here ($g_2 - g_1$) are the measured values of gravity (acceleration of gravity) at two subsequent observation points along the well in unit of mGal; σ is the density (in unit of g/cm^3) of a layer with thickness Δh (in km).

Thus, it is possible to study changes in the density of rocks along the borehole, which is necessary information when searching for mineral deposits. In addition, if there is any geological body, structure or ore body along the well, or these geological objects are located near the well, the location of these objects can be determined from the results of measurements. The figure below shows the results of modeling the gravitational field from a homogeneous geological body in the form of a ball during observations along the well (Fig. 3). As can be seen, the geological body lies

Fig 3. Calculation of the gravity field model in borehole gravimetry

at a depth of 5 km and at this depth the gravity curve changes its sign from plus to minus passing through the zero point directly opposite the center of the ball (Fig. 4).

Fig 4. Gravity curve along the well

Thus, it is possible to estimate the depth of the geological body. The same picture is observed in the results of field well observations along the well crossing the sulfide ore body. The excess density of sulfide ores relative to the limestones enclosing the ore body varies within $0.9\text{--}1.5\text{ g/cm}^3$. When approaching the sulfide

body, the gravity anomaly increases, reaching $+1.4\text{ mGal}$, and when crossing the body, it decreases sharply and, passing through zero, forms a minimum of -1.8 mGal . The asymmetry of the Δg curve well emphasizes the irregular shape of the body (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Curve Δg along a mine shaft crossing a sulfide ore body (according to D. R. Rogers.), [7]

In the case of underground gravity surveys carried out in mines or mine workings, observations are made along a straight line at a certain depth. If observations are made at different depths, then corrections for height are introduced and a correction for the upper intermediate layer is taken into account, which reduces the value of gravity. However, it should be noted that with an increase in the observation depth, the value of gravity increases when the observation point approaches the geological ore and changes its sign to the opposite when

passing through the center of gravity of the body. In addition, measurements in mine workings provide additional material for interpretation, allowing more accurate determination of body parameters. Consider the results of field gravimetric observations at one of the copper pyrite deposits, carried out on the day surface and in mine workings at depths of 190 and 250 m, which made it possible to trace the contour of the ore body (Fig. 6) [7].

Fig. 6. Anomalies in the force of gravity of a sulfide ore body observed on the day surface and in mine workings (according to I. N. Kaptsova), [7].

As can be seen, the deeper the line of observation, i.e. when approaching the desired ore body, the values of gravity increase, and the curve itself shifts to the right, which indicates the inclination of the elongated ore body. For a more visual representation of the desired ore body, we will perform a digital transformation of the gravity curves observed at different depths. To do this, we first take the values of gravity at the charac-

teristic points for each of the curves and digitize the coordinates of the observation points in the “digit” mode of the SURFER graphics program and get a “data” file (Table 1). On the basis of this file, a “grid” file was created, with the help of which a gravity map was built along the section crossing the ore deposit (Fig. 7). Then this map was compared with the original section of the ore deposit (Fig. 8). As can be seen from the figure, this map more clearly reflects the shape and direction of the

ore body itself. However, it should be noted that when approaching the profil relative to the observation to the line of observation passing through the center of gravity of the ore body, the sign of the value of gravity changes

to the opposite (İsgandarov and Seyidov, 2022),[6]. This fact explains the relative shift of the gravity maximum on the section map (see Fig. 8).

Table 1

Gravity values and their coordinates

X, in	Y, in	$\Delta g, mGal$
153.6585	489.7349	1
579.4445	484.8964	1
228.1711	489.7349	2
507.835	487.7995	2
318.1667	488.7672	3
417.8393	488.7672	3
307.5221	378.45	6
325.9083	380.3853	6.5
356.8745	378.45	6
291.0713	379.4177	5
383.0023	378.45	5
279.4589	379.4177	4
400.4208	378.45	4
269.782	379.4177	3
418.807	377.4823	3
230.1064	379.4177	2
444.9348	377.4823	2
206.8818	378.45	1
465.2564	376.5146	1
499.1258	378.45	0
520.4151	377.4823	-1
562.026	374.5792	-1.5
372.3577	343.6129	6.5
353.0038	344.5806	6
399.4531	343.6129	6
337.5206	342.6452	5
412.0332	342.6452	5
336.5529	342.6452	4
435.2579	342.6452	4
317.199	342.6452	3
466.2241	342.6452	3
304.619	344.5806	2
481.7072	341.6775	2
279.4589	343.6129	1
514.6089	341.6775	1

Fig.7. Gravity map along a section crossing an ore deposit.

Fig.8. Comparison of the gravity map with the section of the ore deposit

Conclusion:

1. Analysis of the results of underground gravimetric work in mines and wells carried out in various regions and areas. Possibility and effectiveness of underground gravity exploration for delineation of ore bodies and other accumulations of mineral deposits is shown.

2. A model gravimetric field along the well for a homogeneous geological body in the form of a ball was calculated and built on a computer. It is shown that the gravity curve changes its sign when the point of observation of the center of gravity of the geological body passes. This fact is shown on specific field material

3. Digital processing of the observed values of gravity was performed using the example of a sulfide deposit. A map of the gravity section was built using a graphical editor in a modern interface, which more clearly shows the shape and direction of the desired ore body in comparison with the profile of mine observations of gravity.

4. Gravity exploration is an economically advantageous geophysical method and therefore it is recommended to use underground gravity exploration in many areas, including Azerbaijan.

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